

Results indicated that amino acid requirements of *N. lugens*, mainly total concentration, differed across the three populations (see table). The Mudgo population required the highest concentration (4.0–4.8%).

The three populations differed in adaptation to variation in amino acids. It is possible that amino acids are an important biochemical basis for resistance to *N. lugens* in rice and play an impor-

tant role in the formation of new host-related populations or biotypes of the insect.

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Effects of amino acid composition of the diet on the performance of three host-related populations of *Nilaparvata lugens*.^a

Factor	<i>N. lugens</i> population	Emergence rate	Proportion of brachypterous adults	Weight of newly molted adult		Nymphal duration	
				Female	Male	Female	Male
Overall amino acid content (%)	TNI	** (3.2–2.4)	ns	ns	b	ns	ns
	Mudgo	b	*	**	***	***	***
	ASD7	b	(2.4)	ns	(4.0–4.8)	(4.0–4.8)	(4.0–4.8)
Eaa-nEaa	TNI	ns	ns	ns	b	***	***
	Mudgo	b	ns	***	*	(50:50)	(50:50)
	ASD7	b	*	*	(50:50–42:58)	(50:50)	(50:50)
Interaction	TNI	ns	ns	ns	**	**	ns
	Mudgo	*	ns	***	ns	***	***
	ASD7	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	**

^ans = no significant effect ($P > 0.05$); *, **, and *** = significant effect at 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 level, respectively (F test). Numbers in parentheses are the optimum overall amino acid level (%) or Eaa-nEaa determined by Duncan's multiple range test. ^bMain effects are not examined when the interaction term made up a large proportion of the ANOVA total sum of squares.

Effects of genotypes and insecticide application on tungro disease incidence and grain yield of rice

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Rice tungro disease (RTD) is a devastating viral disease of rice caused by rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). It can be managed by controlling its insect vectors—green leafhoppers (*Nephotettix* spp.). However, there

is still a debate on RTD management through insecticide application. Ganapathy et al (2001) and Batay-an and Mancao (2001) have found that RTD could be managed by applying insecticides to control leafhoppers. However, this has not been universally

accepted among research workers. Villareal (2001) reported that leafhopper control by insecticides is not a solution to the tungro problem as application of insecticides to control leafhopper vectors of RTD cannot be justified in areas where inoculum sources are

not present. In view of these findings, more studies are needed under different agroecological zones so that a more suitable approach to control RTD can be developed.

A field experiment was conducted at ARS in Siruguppa, Karnataka, India, during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons. The experiment was carried out in a split-plot design with three replications. Treatments consisted of three genotypes in the main plots (6 × 4 m) and two disease management levels in the subplots (3 × 4 m)—disease management (DM), in which insecticide monocrotophos was sprayed, and no disease management (NM), in which no insecticide was sprayed.

Soil at the experimental site was deep black with pH 8.0 and available N, P, and K content of 318, 47, and 447 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The crop was fertilized with 150, 75, and 75 kg of N, P, and K ha⁻¹, respectively, of which 50% N and full P and K doses were applied uniformly as basal dressing. The other 50% N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Seedlings (30 d old) were transplanted at 20 × 10-cm spacing with 2–3 seedlings hill⁻¹. Monocrotophos (360 g ai ha⁻¹) was applied at 40 and 55 d after transplanting. Disease incidence was recorded 15 d after the second spray by fixing a 1-m² area at random in each plot and disease severity was scored using the 0–9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (IRRI 1980). After harvest, grain yield (t ha⁻¹) was recorded from a 2.8 × 3.6-m plot.

The analysis indicated that year significantly affected grain yield and disease incidence. Results for each year are reported separately in the table. Both grain

yield and percent disease incidence differed significantly in relation to genotype and DM. The interaction between genotype and DM was significant for percent disease incidence (PDI). DM recorded a higher grain yield than NM in all three genotypes studied for both years. PDI in IR64 and IET10719 was significantly higher in NM than in DM for both years. Vikramarya had no disease incidence and had a higher grain yield than IET10719 and IR64 during both years. The high yield of Vikramarya may be attributed to its tungro virus resistance, while the lower yields of IR64 and IET10719 may be due to the higher disease incidence observed.

From these studies, it is evident that Vikramarya can be grown in RTD-endemic areas. When growing either IET10719 or IR64 in the Tungabhadra project command area of Karnataka, where RTD appears sporadically every year, insecticide spraying can be adopted.

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RTD incidence (%) and grain yield (t ha⁻¹) as influenced by genotype and disease management level at Siruguppa, Karnataka, India, 1998-99 wet seasons.

Year	Genotype	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
		With disease management	No disease management	With disease management	No disease management
1998	IR64	37.6 (6.2) ^o	60.7 (7.9)*	3.2	2.7*
	IET10719	26.7 (5.3)	48.1 (7.0)*	4.2	3.2*
	Vikramarya	0.0 (1.0)	00.0 (1.0) ns	6.8	6.6 ns
	CD (5%)		0.17		0.67
1999	IR64	17.0 (4.2)	34.1 (5.9)*	3.7	2.8*
	IET10719	19.3 (4.5)	30.4 (5.6)*	3.2	2.5*
	Vikramarya	00.0 (1.0)	00.0 (1.0) ns	5.7	5.2*
	CD (5%)		0.49		1.23

^oNumbers in parentheses are square root-transformed values. The value in the no-disease management subplot is significantly different (*P*<0.05) from that in the disease management subplot (LSD test).